

India

Reduction in cladoceran taxonomic and functional diversity after restoration of a shallow urban reservoir in India.

Mihir R. Kulkarni¹, Sameer M. Padhye^{2*}

¹ Department of Zoology, Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune, India.

Current address: Laboratory for Conservation of Endangered Species, CSIR-CCMB, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

² Biologia Life Science LLP, Ahmednagar, India

*Email: sameer.m.padhye@gmail.com

Worldwide, anthropogenic disturbances are decreasing species and functional diversity of various ecosystems including aquatic biomes (Carpenter et al. 2011). Small freshwater reservoirs are commonly created in or around urban regions as sources of potable/usable water, and recreational and/or aquaculture spaces. Additionally, they act as buffers against environmental fluctuations and serve as biodiversity reserves (Jurczak et al. 2019). Due to the land-use patterns in their surroundings, they often face disturbances like structural modifications, extrinsic nutrient loading, high siltation and inorganic pollution, which trigger undesirable phenomena such as eutrophication and algal blooms. Such deteriorating health of these habitats prompts implementation of restoration measures, which are often undertaken without proper ecological assessment, and can in turn

Fig. 2: A-D: Some of the cladoceran species found in the early phase of the collection. A. *Latonopsis australis*; B. *Oxyurella singalensis*; C. *Coronatella rectangula*; D. *Leberis punctatus*.

over the years, leading to severe eutrophication of the reservoir. The subsequent restoration work was carried out between 2008-2013 which included de-siltation, re-contouring, construction of a retaining wall and an artificial island etc. (Yardi et al. 2019 for details). Prior to this intervention, the lake had a rich diversity of habitats and biota, ranging from macrophytes and aquatic invertebrates to birds. Post restoration, the lake surface was covered entirely by *Pistia* and *Eichornia* species (Fig. 1C).

We collected zooplankton from Pashan reservoir during 2009/2010 as part of a larger survey, following a qualitative sampling of multiple sites in the littoral/sub-littoral regions using hand and tow nets. Following a similar strategy, we sampled the reservoir in 2016. Based on the phases of restoration, we categorized the samples into 'early' (2009-2010) and 'late' (2016) phases and

Ceriodaphnia cornuta Sars, 1885 s.lat. and *Moina micrura* Kurz, 1874 were seen in both the phases. In addition, functional groups, Functional richness and redundancy were also significantly reduced from the early to the late phase.

Our observations on the cladoceran fauna in the two phases indicated an alteration of community composition driven entirely by species loss, leading to a decrease in functional diversity. This could have occurred due to a combination of factors including a) alteration of habitat structure (e.g. topographic changes, destruction of habitats), b) removal of aquatic macrophytes, c) removal of egg banks, d) fish introduction and e) increased levels of untreated sewage. These impacts also showed a loss of regionally rare species from the late phase community, a characteristic of biotic homogenization which has been observed in urban habitats facing multiple stressors (Rahel 2002). These data highlight the importance of ecologically informed strategies for urban habitat restoration.

Fig.1: A-B: Pashan water reservoir location; C. Pashan lake in the late phase (2016).

aggravate the situation. Studying the impacts of restoration activities on the local biota is important, although such studies are lacking from India.

We conducted this study to explore the effects of restoration on an urban reservoir in Pune city, India, specifically analyzing the changes in community composition of Cladocera at the taxonomic and functional levels.

Pashan Lake (18°31'59"N; 73°47'18"E) is situated south-west of Pune City, India (Fig. 1A, B), formed due to the damming of a small river (Ramnadi) in the early 1900's. There has been a sustained increase in urbanization around the lake periphery

screened and identified the cladocerans using the latest taxonomical keys. We analyzed the difference in cladoceran species composition using incidence data and used functional traits data (Rizo et al. 2017) to calculate the functional composition, richness and redundancy for both the phases.

A significant taxonomic reduction, both of Cladoceran species and families, was seen from the early phase to the late phase (28 species in early phase, 9 species in the late phase). Species like *Oxyurella singalensis* Daday, 1862, *Coronatella rectangula* Sars, 1862 s.lat. and *Leberis punctatus* Daday, 1898 (Fig. 2) were observed only in the early phase while locally common species like

Funding

This work was funded by the International Society of Limnology (SIL), Tonolli award to SMP in 2015. A preprint of the complete study is available at: <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2021.06.18.448979v1>

References

- Carpenter SR, Stanley EH, Vander Zanden MJ. 2011. State of the world's freshwater ecosystems: physical, chemical, and biological changes. Annual Review of Environment and Resources 36: 75-99.
- Jurczak T, Wojtal-Frankiewicz A, Frankiewicz P, Kaczkowski Z, Oleksińska Z, Bednarek A, Zalewski M. 2019. Comprehensive approach to restoring urban recreational reservoirs. Part 2 – Use of zooplankton as indicators for the ecological quality assessment. Science of The Total Environment 653: 1623-1640.
- Rahel FJ. 2002. Homogenization of freshwater faunas. Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics 33(1): 291-315.
- Rizo E, Gu Y, Papa RDS, Dumont HJ, Han BP. 2017. Identifying functional groups and ecological roles of tropical and subtropical freshwater Cladocera in Asia. Hydrobiologia 799(1): 83-99.
- Yardi KD, Bharucha E, Girade S. 2019. Post-restoration monitoring of water quality and avifaunal diversity of Pashan Lake, Pune, India using a citizen science approach. Freshwater Science, 38(2): 332-341.
- <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4889827>